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МІСЦЕ СТУДЕНТСЬКОГО НАУКОВОГО ГУРТКА У СИСТЕМІ ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ АДАПТАЦІЇ

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STUDENT SCIENTIFIC GROUP WORK WITHIN THE SYSTEM OF PROFESSIONAL ADAPTATION IN UKRAINE

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Анотація

Теоретичною основою поняття «адаптація» є уявлення про неї як про постійний процес активного пристосування індивідуума до умов навколишнього середовища, який торкається всіх рівнів функціонування людини. Робота в студентській науковій групі, залучення студентів до виконання науково-дослідної роботи відіграє велику роль в соціально-психологічній адаптації студента. Метою нашої роботи стало порівняти соціально-психологічну адаптацію у студентів, які приймали активну участь в роботі гуртків та виконували науково-дослідні роботи під час навчання в університеті зі студентами, які не були залучені до цього виду роботи. В результаті дослідження було виявлено, що адаптація у студентів обох груп більше 80%. Цей результат не наближений до 100%, тому що, незважаючи на 6 рік навчання в університеті, студенти мають ряд особливостей в цей період, які впливають на їх адаптаційний рівень. В 1-й групі ми отримали цей показник незначно вищим на 7% за контрольну групу. Це можна пояснити тим, що відсоток студентів, які активно залучались до науково-дослідної роботи, визначились з подальшою спеціалізацією та вже працюють в тому напрямку. В дослідній групі адаптовані студенти частіше проявляють інтернальність, сприймають всі зміни, що відбуваються з ними, як результат власної діяльності (входження в режим роботи, самостійне складання графіка навчання, здатність встигати додатково навчатися та виконувати науково-дослідну роботу). Лише 9% в цій групі студентів сприймають події, які відбуваються, як вплив інших сил (судьба, випадок та інше). У контрольній групі цей відсоток вищий в два рази, це може проявлятися в житті студента у вигляді порушення самоорганізації. Емоційна комфортність в групі студентів, які займаються НДР значно вища. Так в першій групі показник складає 85% [75,48–94,52] на відміну від другої групи 67% [60,53–73,47] ($p \leq 0,05$). Перевага позитивних емоцій, відчуття благополуччя пов'язана з визначенням подальшого напрямку навчання, отриманням, за рахунок науково-дослідної роботи в гуртках, перших професійних перемог, позитивною самореалізацією у вибраному напрямку. В контрольній групі більше 1/3 студентів переживає емоційний дискомфорт на цьому рівні навчання, що значно обтяжує процес навчання. Отриманні дані в контрольній групі свідчать про майже однаковий відсоток рівня самосприйняття та сприйняття інших. Студенти демонструють дружнє відношення до своїх сокурсників, що свідчить про прийняття оточення, схвалення їх життєвої позиції, в цілому позитивного відношення до себе оточуючих. У студентів дослідної групи виявляється позитивний полюс самосприйняття, що відображає ступінь доброзичливості до себе та відображає здатність оцінювати свої сильні та слабкі сторони. Більш низький показник прагнення до домінування в групі студентів, які відвідували гурток обумовлений

напевно більшою здатністю роботи в команді. Отже, ми бачимо, що студенти, які відвідують гуртки, додатково виконують НДР більше використовують свої адаптаційні можливості.

Abstract

The correct approach to organization of student's self-learning process is of uppermost importance for successful higher education. Classroom work in higher education institutions aims at setting and giving direction functions of a teaching/learning process, and it is a student who is responsible for active knowledge acquisition through different means. Participating in different students' societies and carrying out scientific research work may become the most appropriate forms of active acquisition. Systematic work in students' societies performing research independently as well as in close cooperation with scientific advisors satisfies two main criteria of social and psychological adaptation: satisfaction from independently obtained results of scientific research and social success, which presupposes conquering new life conditions and gaining respect from fellow students and teaching staff. The theoretical basis of the concept of adaptation is the idea of a continuous process of active adaptation of the individual to the environment that concerns all levels of human functioning. Participation in student scientific groups plays a major role in the student's socio-psychological adaptation. Results obtained in the course of our research proved that there was statistically valid difference in 6th-year students' adaptation. It should be pointed out that the 6th-year is the time of the so-called "third crisis" of higher education. It appears due to the issue with work allocation and transition from studying to working lifestyle, also comparing possessed and desired knowledge and skills may bring a certain dissonance into student's self-perception. Students consider the influence of their profession on their future welfare. All these issues can be dealt with easier in case of students who have attended scientific societies and groups, who have tried their hands in practical aspects and improved their knowledge. The results of our analysis are the following. The purpose of the paper lies in comparing psychological and social adaptation of students who participate in scientific groups and are engaged in scientific research with that of students who refrain from such activities. Material and methods. To study social and psychological adaptation 154 students were asked to fill in a questionnaire based on the K. Roger and R. Dimond's methodology. Results and discussion. We find that the adaptation in the group of students engaged in the research activity is much higher. Thus, in the first group, the index of emotional comfort is 85%, while the second group has the index of 67%. Researches evaluated the statements about a person, about the way of professional life, experiences, thoughts, habits, behavioral styles on a six-point scale: Adaptation, Self-Perception, Perception of Others, Emotional Comfort, Internality, Domination. Considerable difference between control and experiment groups is established for internality, emotional comfort, and self-perception and perception of others. Conclusion. The obtained results proved that participation in scientific societies increased students' ability for adaptation and helped to develop a socially and psychologically healthy professional with such grounded qualities as self-respect, self-understanding, independence and assertiveness.

Ключові слова: соціально-психологічна адаптація, студент, студентський науковий гурток.

Keywords: socio-psychological adaptation, student, student scientific circle.

Students graduating from University must possess necessary knowledge and be able to acquire new scientific awareness and diagnostic skills, have logical and quick methodology for finding necessary information, thus, introducing a new and unique "way of functioning". Even more important is to be ready for the profession, ready to adapt to the requirements. A student himself elaborates this process after he gets necessary skills in college. These skills are based on the idea of competitiveness and changing demands of nowadays.

We carried out a research to prove that there is a certain correlation between professional adaptation of students and their involvement in different scientific activities during years of their study. In our opinion, the most consistent and thus profitable kind of students' research work is students' groups and societies. Student Scientific Group (SSG) is an organizational formation at the department, the participants of which constitute a wide range of students of the university, and which is formed taking into account scientific activities of the department and in accordance with the thematic plans of the department [1]. Scientific societies at the university departments are created with the purpose of realization of creative scientific potential of students and their participation in research work and programs worked on at the University, as well as for the purpose of fulfilling scientific, educational and creative professional activities.

To study social and psychological adaptation K. Roger and R. Dimond's methodology was used [3]. In the process of research 154 students were asked to fill in a questionnaire based on the given methodology. The proportion is the following: 100 questionnaires were filled in by students not engaged in any scientific group and 54 – by students who actively participated in SSG. The studies were carried out in compliance with the basic provisions of the " Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects", approved by WMA Declaration of Helsinki (1964-2013), ICH GCP (1996), EEC Directive No. 609 (dated 24.11.1986). , Ministry of Health of Ukraine Orders No. 690 dated September 23, 2009, No. 944 dated December 14, 2009, No. 616 dated August 3, 2012. Statistical processing of the received data was carried out by the method of determining the confidence interval where the value of $p \leq 0.05$ was accepted for the probability level [2]. All our conclusions are proven by the results the questionnaire provides.

Researches evaluated the statements about a person, about his/her way of professional life, experiences, thoughts, habits, behavioral styles on a six-point scale: Adaptation, Self-Perception, Perception of Others, Emotional Comfort, Internality, Domination (see Table 1).

Table 1

Representation of Structural Components of Students' Adaptation

Components of Students' Adaptation	Representation of Students' Adaptation in Group 1 (engaged in scientific activities)	Representation of Students' Adaptation in Group 2 (not engaged in any scientific activities)
Adaptation (A)	89%	82%
Self-perception (S)	83%	69%
Perception of others (L)	72%	67%
Emotional Comfort (E)	81%	69%
Internality (I)	93%	82%
Domination (D)	38%	52%

Although all students were on their 5th year of study their adaptation is not close to 100%. In both groups this factor is high, more than 80%, but still students have some issues to overcome. The reason is future working place allocation process that is considerably stressful for students. This period of study is defined in psychological sources as the third crisis period that explains lower level of adaptation than expected during the last year of study. Group 1 shows higher level than Group 2, which is explained by the fact that they have had more possibilities to decide what they are apt to do in SSG.

Considerable difference between control and experiment groups is established for internality, i.e. 11%. And this component has the highest value among others with students engaged in scientific groups, showing that they are ready to accept responsibility more readily than their colleagues. In control group students would more easily find faults with destiny, circumstances, weather etc., which leads to certain self-organization disfunctioning.

Emotional comfort is another segment showing considerable difference between students engaged in scientific societies and those who are not. So in the first group the figure is 85% [75,48-94,52] as opposed to the second group is 67% [60,53-73,47] ($p \leq 0,05$). One third of students from the control group feel emotional discomfort during their last year of study making the whole process harder and less resultative for them. Experiment group students due to their first professional challenges and success in scientific research feel comfortable in terms of self-realization and further career development.

Difference in self-perception and perception of others within two groups highlights that all activities in SSG help students to concentrate on their own personalities and achievements without any compensation in regard to respect towards colleagues. Together with lower figure in terms of dominance seeking it shows that SSG actually help to adapt to teamwork and build healthy professional relations. So in the first group the

index is 84% [74,22-93,78], while in the second group it is 68% [63,34-72,66] ($p \leq 0,05$).

Domination in the first group is accounted for 38% [25,06-50,94], in the second group – 54% [44,33-63,66] ($p \leq 0,05$).

The overall result proves that participation in SSG increases students' ability for adaptation and helps to develop a socially and psychologically healthy professional with such grounded qualities as self-respect, self-understanding, independence and assertiveness.

Conclusions

1. Adaption of students greatly depends on their readiness for real life tasks and previous experience in their professional sphere.

2. Participation in scientific societies is a means of getting students involved into practical experience under the control of mentors.

3. Experience in SSC participation helps to acquire skills in independent scientific research work and improve quality of general medicine studying.

4. Students taking part in SSC get possibility to master their chosen profession, acquire necessary research skills to proceed with scientific research work after graduation, simultaneously getting necessary psychological background for self-assurance, emotional comfort and internality.

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